

Aspects of Human Development Job Satisfaction among Youth in Development Sector: A study on PGDRDM students of NIRDPR

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Abstract

Human resource managers of the present generation find it very difficult to ignore the concept of Job Satisfaction in a period when demand for meaningful work is on the rise. There is immense competition for scarce resources that resulted in increased labour cost. Organizations hence prefer to reduce labour turnover without having to hire more employees.

This can be done only if the companies can retain the interests of existing employees. But job satisfaction is dependent upon a variety of factors more so in this digital era where youth trained in utilizing Information Communication Technology do have information about bright career opportunities.

Youth in any sector, whether it is Information Technology, Manufacturing or development sector prefer to continue in their area of interest according to their level of Job satisfaction. The present paper focuses upon the job satisfaction levels of the present day youth in development sector.

Through structured Questionnaire method 60 Post Graduate Diploma in Rural Development alumni students currently working in development sector have been assessed. The results indicated that youth in this digital era are having high expectations about their career and growth prospects and are ready to accept any kind of challenges.

Key Words

Development professionals, Job satisfaction, Postgraduate Diploma in Rural Development, Youth in development sector

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Introduction:

Job satisfaction is one important aspect necessary for success of an organization. Job satisfaction describes how content an individual is with his /her job. The happier people are within their job, the more satisfied they are said to be. Job satisfaction has been defined as a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job (Locke, 1976); an affective reaction to one's job (Cranny, Smith & Stone, 1992); and an attitude towards one's job (Brief, 1998). Job satisfaction is defined as the extent to which people like (satisfied) or dislike (dissatisfied) their jobs (Spector, 1997).

Job satisfaction is a complex variable and is influenced by situational factors of the job as well as the dispositional characteristics of the individual (Sharma & Ghosh, 2006). It is defined as the positive emotional response to the job situation resulting from attaining what the employee wants from the job. This implies that job satisfaction can be captured by either a one-dimensional concept of Global Job satisfaction or a Multi Dimensional faceted construct of job satisfaction capturing different aspects of it that can vary independently.

Factors effecting Job Satisfaction:**Organizational Factors:****A) Monetary factors:**

1. **Salary and Perks:** This consist salary structure, perquisites, bonus, incentives, free or subsidized food, subsidized commutation etc.
2. **Promotion and Benefits:** This includes of future job prospects, stability, job security, awards or rewards, performance bonus etc.

B) Non-Monetary:

1. **Nature of work:** This includes the nature of job, quality and sufficiency of the equipment provided, necessary health care, production targets, responsibility and level of authority etc.
2. **Job Security:** Requirement of worker's services for a longer period, sense of belongingness, fulfilment of family and personal needs for considerably longer period creates relaxation in the mind of workers.
3. **Relations with Seniors:** Here communication, level of discretion, trust, empowerment, understanding between the worker and supervisor is the main concern.
4. **Relations with Co-workers:** Mutual co-operation, comparative division of work, formal and informal groups, moral support, team attitude, seniority issues, inter-personal problems and conflicts are the important sub-factors.
5. **Autonomy:** Autonomy is defined as the degree to which an individual is free to make decisions about his or her work environment (Van de Ven & Ferry, 1980).

6. Career development opportunities**7. Overall corporate culture****8. The variety of work****B) External factors:**

- i) Personal: Family issues
- ii) Social: Religious issues
- iii) Overall corporate culture

Job Satisfaction among development professionals:

The development profession has experienced a critical scarcity of professionals. The retention of development professional is challenging for institutions not only for Asian countries, but also for many different countries as described in studies conducted in the United States of America and the United Kingdom (Vermeulen, 2008).

Job Satisfaction among development professionals in India:

India too experienced a drastic shortage of social workers and development professionals, which has affected many social welfare organisations and community based organisations. Development professionals mostly youth are observed to be frequently switching their jobs from one institution to another as are not able to retain their interest in one particular employment.

According to Adlem, many reasons contribute to the high turnover of social workers. These include poor working conditions, poor compensation for work, lack of resources and support, and increased demands for services. Hence social workers are experiencing work stress, burnout, decreasing job satisfaction and a lack of positive work engagement (Adlem, 2007).

Literature review

Phathara-On Wesarat et al, 2013 in his study showed that the NGO professionals had given high values on the subjective aspects of work because they were seeking fulfilment from work, while the objective aspects of work were seen to be less important to them.

Cole, Panchanadeswaran, and Daining (2004) cited Siefert et al. (1991) study of health care social workers, family preservation workers, child welfare, community mental health, and family service workers found that high levels of perceived efficacy provided a direct correlation to higher levels of job satisfaction. Cole, Panchanadeswaran, and Daining 2004, also cited a study completed by Davis-Sacks et al. (1985), which drew from a sample of child welfare workers, finding that supportive supervision was associated with increased levels of job satisfaction.

Gregory C. Petty and Ernest W. Brewer, 2005, The purpose of this study was to explore the association between overall job satisfaction and selected demographic variables among 332 employees of a youth development organization. The Job Satisfaction Index (JSI) was used to measure the level of job satisfaction, and demographic information was obtained via a questionnaire developed by the researchers. Data analysis procedures included descriptive statistics, Spearman's rho, Pearson r, t tests, and analysis of variance (ANOVA). Results indicated no significant relationships or differences ($p < 0.05$) between job satisfaction and demographic variables. These findings have implications for future research on job satisfaction and employee retention in youth development organizations.

Getahun Kassa, 2016, This study assessed the level of job satisfaction and the factors associated with it among agricultural extension workers (DAs) in South West Ethiopia. Primary data were collected by using structured questionnaire from 170 DAs selected by using simple random sampling technique. DAs' job satisfaction was measured on an ordered 5-point Likert scale. Due to the categorical nature of the dependent variable, ordinal logit regression model was used to identify the factors affecting level of job satisfaction of DAs in the study area. The findings of the study revealed that the majority of DAs' were dissatisfied with their job. The major causes for DAs' job dissatisfaction were work overload, extremely low payment, difficult & disadvantaged work environment, poor social status, and poor interpersonal relationship with co-workers. However, a significant positive association was observed between job satisfaction and promotion policy. It is, therefore, important that the government should devise multiple package schemes to enhance the satisfaction level of DAs'.

Philip et al., 2011, This study analyses the determinants of job satisfaction among a sample of social workers. Factors determining variance in levels of job satisfaction were investigated using mean job satisfaction scores. The analysis uses six independent variables (age, career tenure, job tenure, sex, salary and whether they were in private practice or worked for an agency/organization). A number of these variables were found to have an effect on the level of job satisfaction experienced by this sample of social workers.

Vishal Soodan and Akhilesh Chandra Pandey, 2017, Leadership styles in recent studies have been debated significantly but their role in contributing job satisfaction of employees have not been addressed by the researchers. Therefore, a study was conducted to assess the impact of leadership styles on job satisfaction of employees in the two NGO's (Non Government Organisations) HIFEED and HESCO from Uttarakhand through an empirical study. NGO's in India involve diverse activities ranging from training facilities and independent trainers providing non-formal education, grant-making organizations, community development organizations, microfinance associations, self-help groups, and organization addressing public health. In the study, leadership styles were studied as participative, supportive and instrumental. Results show that supportive style of leadership was predominantly followed by managers. Participative leadership

style positively impacts job satisfaction followed by supportive style of leadership. But instrumental leadership style was found to have a negative impact on the job satisfaction of employees.

Charity Tinofirei, 2011, conducted a study on job performance of employees in the humanitarian non-profit sector. This study was conducted on 127 respondents from Zimbabwe, Southern Africa. Researcher reported that the absence of automatic job promotions for high performing individuals could negatively affect high performing individuals who feel they are not rewarded for superior performance.

From the above fact, it also becomes clear that studies on job satisfaction had been conducted across the world including India as well. In India however, studies were reported from different parts of the country. But the numbers of studies reported from development sectors are scarce. Hence, this justified in favour of the present study on job satisfaction among youth in development sector.

Thus this study brings to light important facts based on the result analysis of this group of youth who are continuing to work with development sector. The results of this study will assist the sector to sustain the interests of their employees and improve their level of job satisfaction.

Research Questions:

- What is the impact of choosing organisation in gaining Opportunities for Personal growth and Development
- What is the impact of gender on job-satisfaction?

Objectives of the Study:

Following objectives were framed:

- To study the organizational factors of job satisfaction and their contribution development professional job satisfaction.
- To examine the impact of gender on job-satisfaction
- To offer effective suggestions for improving the levels of job satisfaction

Methodology

Research Design

The job satisfaction was considered as dependent variables. The socioeconomic and digital distraction variables were considered as independent variables. An attempt was made to understand job satisfaction in the context of organizational and socio-economic factors. Hence, this study followed descriptive research design.

The Sample Population: Population in the present study comprises of the Alumina of PGDRDM, NIRD&PR, Hyderabad.

Sample Design: As per the nature of this study convenience, sampling approach was adopted.

Tools and Techniques of Data Collection:

Research using surveying through google self instructed questionnaire was applied as the core methodology to acquire the raw data from the Alumni of PGDRDM students currently working in development sector.

The questionnaire was developed with an intention to judge the responses of the students in connection with all the parameters influencing the job satisfaction of the development professional. The questions are pertaining to these parameters

- 1) Good Perks and Benefits,
- 2) Good Work Environment(Physical),
- 3) Opportunities for Personal growth and Development,
- 4) Job Security,
- 5) Flexi Working hours,

The questionnaire contains 15 questions in all about the parameters for getting information from the respondents. The total 15 questions are divided in six parameters. Every parameter has five questions in the form of Likert Scale. (Five rating scale from 1 to 5 starting from 1= not important ; 2= Slightly important ; 3= Moderately important ; 4= Very important ; 5= Extremely important at the end).

Results and Discussions:

Table 1: Good Salary offer

Response	Percent
Not Important	8.7
Moderately important	21
Very important	52
Extremely important	17
Total	100

Factors that increase job satisfaction among development professional include satisfaction with salary. Job satisfaction decreases for social workers who have a poor salary (Cole, Panchanadeswaran and Daining, 2004:2). Most of the respondents were 52% and 17.4 said that good salary is very & extremely important in his/her life.

Table 2: Rewards

Response	Percent
Slightly important	8.7
Moderately important	39.1
Very important	52.2
Total	100.0

Fitts (2006) found the best predictor for job satisfaction was promotional opportunities and Rewards. The best predictor for changing jobs was low financial reward. From Table -2, 52.2 per cent respondent said that rewards and promotional opportunities in very important and 39.1 per cent said that rewards are moderate important in job satisfaction.

Table 3: Opportunities to participate in decision-making

Response	Percent
Moderately important	21.7
Very important	34.8
Extremely important	43.5
Total	100.0

When employees are more active in decision-making they feel more engaged, which leads to higher satisfaction and lower turnover rates (Peltier & Dahl, 2009:10). In this study 43.5% of the respondents felt

they were participate in decision making affecting their work and hence they are extremely important for the organization

There were 34.8% respondents who felt that they were participating in decision making affecting organization and themselves.

Bar diagram indicates the score of males in comparison to females on the items of Job- security. Males scored high on the item of job security. On general job satisfaction, also males scored higher than females. Men are found to be more concerned about job security than women.

Table 4 : Opportunities Personal growth

Gender	Mean
Male	4.39
Female	4.00
Total	4.30

There was significant difference on the item of opportunities in personal growth between males and females.

Table 5: Flexi Working hours

Response	Percent
Not important	4.3
Slightly important	13.0
Moderately important	34.8
Very important	26.1
Extremely important	21.7
Total	100.0

This statistics tells us tentative trend of the data. 21.7 per cent respondent liked flexi working hours in organisation. Flexi working hours effect women more than men. However, the sample of youth seems to be giving only moderate importance to this aspect.

Table 6: Correlation between overall Job Satisfaction and Job Satisfaction Indicator

Indicator	Job satisfaction
Rewards	.612*
Autonomy	.261*
Colleague support	.269*
Supervisor support	.380*

Table 6 show the data from the correlation analysis, showing the relationship between overall job satisfaction and the four-job indicators. In general, the data show that job satisfaction first is associated with rewards (.612).

From the above table it's observed that all the computed value of P are satisfying as all have a positive note. It can be further seen that the first indicator (Rewards) is on a higher reflection as the value is greater than other factors ie 0.612.

Suggestion

- The working environment needs to be made more pleasant, relaxed, cordial and friendly, so that the development professional would feel as a family member in the organisation.
- Director should be unbiased and should give equal opportunity to all the development professional for skill enhancement. Director should show positive interest in the feelings of his/her subordinates.
- Work assignments should be fully explained.
- A good work should be recognized through awards and rewards.
- More research needs to be focused on retaining development professional for the profession.
- There is a need for further additional research in the social sector realm relating to enhancing job satisfaction.

To conclude

Job satisfaction is therefore the deciding factor that help an employee to make up his/her mind whether to continue in the organization or quit. Results of the study clearly indicate that employee turnover could not be stopped unless their needs are satisfied. Gender based needs of employees also cannot be ignored. Further topic of job satisfaction among development profession will continue to draw great debate for discussion among development professionals.

As the research still continues to remain minimal with regard to avenues for promoting job satisfaction of development professionals, it is now time that the institutions of social work take notice and prepare future professional with the best possible tools to lead.

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